

Case Report

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Multidisciplinary Management of Post Cancrum Oris Facial Deformity in a Nine Year Old at a Tertiary Hospital, North Central Nigeria: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Cancrum oris is known by various other names such as Noma and it is a rapidly progressive, frequently gangrenous infection of the mouth and face. It affects poor and malnourished children in sub-Saharan countries. The underlying causes for this disease are predominantly poor sanitation and malnutrition. The case was a 9 year old male pupil, who was earlier treated for Noma 2 years prior to presentation in the Benue State University Teaching. At that time he presented with history of swelling of the right eye, protrusion and difficulty seeing with the same eye all for a duration of 3 months. The healing resulted in facial deformity with right sided ugly scar of the cheek, trismus, inability to open the mouth and the right eye. This was the setting that required the multi-disciplinary approach to the surgical management including the airway, anaesthesia and the surgery proper resulting in a satisfactory outcome.

Keywords: Cancrum Oris; Facial Deformity Multi-disciplinary; Management

INTRODUCTION

Cancrum Oris is known by other names such as Noma, Fusospirochaetal Gangrene, Necrotizing Ulcerative Stomatitis as well as Stomatitis Gangrenosa.¹ It is a fast progressive, often gangrenous, infection of the mouth and face.² The mucous membranes of the mouth develop ulcers, and quick, painful tissue degeneration follows, which can degrade tissues and bones in the face.³ Cancrum Oris affects particularly poor and malnourished

children in Sub-Saharan countries and other tropical regions. The underlying causes for this disease are principally poor sanitation and malnutrition.^{2,4} This disease is observed mostly in areas where the social standards are low and hygiene is poor.⁵ Childhood cases are common mainly in developing countries, while adult cases are rare and reported largely in industrialized countries, where the disease is considered to be only a clinical curiosity^{6,7}

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Children between the ages of 2-9 years are frequently affected, although some cases among adults have been described.^{8,9,10}

The progression of the disease can be stopped with the use of antibiotics and enhanced nutrition; however, its physical effects are permanent and may require Oral and Maxillofacial surgery or Reconstructive Plastic surgery to repair. Reconstruction is usually very challenging and should be deferred until full recovery usually up to one year following initial intervention.¹¹

Children as well as other Noma survivors in Africa are aided by a few international charitable organizations, such as *Facing Africa*, a UK registered charity that helps affected Ethiopians, and Swiss charity *Winds of Hope*. There is one dedicated Noma Hospital in Nigeria, the Noma Children Hospital in Sokoto, staffed by resident and visiting medical teams.

This case is being reported to highlight the multidisciplinary approach to the management of a child who developed a facial deformity and severe trismus following treatment for Noma. First was the management of the patient's airway by the Anaesthetic and the Ear, Nose and Throat surgery (ENT) teams, followed by the collaboration that took place between the Maxillofacial and the Ophthalmology teams with regards to the reconstructive surgical procedure. These multidisciplinary collaborations resulted in satisfactory anaesthetic and surgical outcomes.

CASE PRESENTATION

In December, 2019, a 7 year old male pupil presented to the Benue State University Teaching Hospital from Gboko with history of swelling of the right eye, protrusion and difficulty seeing with the same eye all for a duration of 3 months. On evaluation by the Ophthalmologists, an impression of Ocular Burkitts to rule out Rhabdomyosarcoma was made.

A computed tomography (CT) scan of the right eye revealed an isodense mass in the right orbit, displacing the globe. With the CT result, attention became focused

on Rhabdomyosarcoma. Patient could not access the prescribed chemotherapy regime owing to financial constraints so parents opted for native treatment. The lesion subsequently progressed such that it became ulcerated with foul smelling purulent discharge which now necessitated the child presenting back to the hospital 3 months later.

Patient was referred to the Maxillofacial Surgeons. The Maxillofacial team found right eye protrusion, oculo-cutaneous fistula with a necrotic base. A diagnosis of Cancrum Oris was made and tissue biopsy specimen was taken from around the lesion under general anaesthesia. Histologic findings shows neurofibromatoma of the right eye. Regular dressing of the ulcer in combination with administration of broad spectrum oral antibiotics resulted in the healing of the ulcer. The healing resulted in facial deformity with right sided ugly scar on the cheek, severe trismus, ectropium of the right lower eyelid with exposure of fornical conjunctiva as well as medial canthal defect and deviation of the nasal bridge.

An assessment of post Cancrum Oris facial deformity with fibrous soft tissue ankylosis of the right jaw and right eye ectropium, was made and patient was booked for surgical correction in April 2021.

Preoperative anaesthetic review revealed a 9 year old boy weighing 23kg. There was no history of comorbidity. There was no abnormality detected on physical examination but for the airway assessment that revealed near complete inability to open the mouth (Mallapati IV). Basic Haematological and Chemical Pathology investigations were normal. Patient was allotted American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification (ASA) 1 and the parents were counseled on general anaesthesia and possible tracheostomy.

While the Anaesthetic and ENT teams were prepared for airway management, the Maxillofacial and the Ophthalmology teams got ready for the reconstructive surgery.

Before patient was brought into the theatre, a pre-anaesthesia equipment check was carried out and induction drugs were withdrawn and labelled. Patient was wheeled

Figure 1: Facial scar highlighted

Figure 2: Inability to close the right eye, inability to open the mouth

into the theatre and an intravenous access was secured with a size 20G cannula with an infusion of 4.3% in 0.18% saline. Baseline vital signs were taken and recorded. With the benefit of experience in airway management in maxillofacial surgery, the anaesthetist was ready for normal intravenous induction and tracheal intubation. At the same time, the ENT team was ready to establish a tracheostomy if the attempt at intubation failed. A tracheostomy set and sizes 5.0mm and 5.5mm cuffed, Portex tracheostomy tubes were kept ready in the event of failed intubation.

Patient was premedicated with 0.02mg/kg of atropine and 0.5mg/kg of pentazocine was administered for analgesia. A smaller than calculated size of tube, 5.0mm was readied because of the anticipated difficult airway.

After patient was pre-oxygenated for 5 minutes using a face mask on a Mapelson F breathing system, anaesthesia was induced with intravenous propofol 2.5mg/kg followed by intravenous suxamethonium 2mg/kg. In spite of the administration of a generous dose of suxamethonium, mouth opening did not improve. Neither an oropharyngeal airway nor a laryngeal mask airway could be inserted into the oral cavity. Nasopharyngeal airway was not readily available. Insertion of a nasopharyngeal airway would have been difficult due to the deviation of the nasal bridge.

With the failure of tracheal intubation, the ENT team performed a tracheostomy while patient was been maintained on Isoflurane in oxygen via the face mask. Patient was positioned; neck was extended with the aid of a shoulder support and the head resting on a head ring. The anterior neck was cleaned up to the chin above and the manubrium sterni below with savlon, spirit and povidon iodine. Patient was draped and a 5cm transverse midline incision made 2-finger- breadths above the suprasternal notch. The incision was deepened to the strap muscles by blunt dissection. The strap muscles were separated at the midline and retracted laterally. The pretracheal fascia covering the trachea and thyroid isthmus was identified and separated. The thyroid isthmus was retracted upwards and a hook was applied to

the second tracheal ring. A vertical incision was made into the trachea at the level of the 3rd and 4th tracheal rings. With the aid of a tracheal dilator, a prepared size 5.5 cuffed, Portex tracheostomy tube was inserted, inflated and the straps anchored around the neck. Haemostasis was maintained and a single skin suture applied on either side of tube to close the skin. Guaze dressing was applied to the tracheostomy wound and the patient was handed back to the anaesthetic team. The face mask was removed and the breathing system was connected to the tracheostomy tube for continuation of anaesthesia.

Patient was manually ventilated until the effect of suxamethonium had worn off. Thereafter, patient was allowed to breathe spontaneously. Maintenance continued with 1-2% isoflurane in oxygen. Monitors included pulse oximeter, noninvasive blood pressure (NIPB) and precordial stethoscope

With the patient sufficiently under anaesthesia, he maxillofacial surgeon undertook a contracture release of the ankylosis of the right temporomandibular joint via the intra oral route. This was followed by the excision of the scar tissue by the surgeons which freed the nasal bridge thereby aligning it properly. The repair of the right eye lid was undertaken by the ophthalmology team. Estimate blood loss was 150 mls and patient was not transfused. 750 mls of IV fluid was infused intra-operatively.

At the end of surgery, isoflurane was cut off and oxygen administered until patient was fully awake. Patient was disconnected from oxygen and observed to be saturating adequately on room air before patient was transferred to the intensive care unit (ICU) for tracheostomy care and haemodynamic monitoring.

Patient was transferred to the ward from the ICU after 3 days, the ENT team decannulated him on the 5th day post operation and he was discharged home on the 10th day post operation with good wound healing.

Figure 5: Surgery in progress

Figure 7: Surgery in progress

Figure 8: After wound closure

Figure 9: After wound closure

Figure 10: After wound dressing

DISCUSSION

Cancrum Oris is a fast progressive, often gangrenous, infection of the mouth and face^{1,2} and affects predominantly poor and malnourished children in sub-Saharan countries and other tropical regions. Our index case is a child of a peasant farmer who was brought up in a rural setting. The pathology also progressed very fast with attendant necrotic tissues and offensive discharge which resulted in the deformity noticed in the patient. Children between the ages of 2-9 years are frequently affected^{8,9,10} This agrees with our patient who was aged 7 years when the disease was noticed.

Its physical effects are permanent and may require oral and maxillofacial surgery or reconstructive plastic surgery to repair which is usually very challenging.¹¹ This is what was seen in this patient who developed an ugly facial scar resulting in inability to close the right eye and

inability to open the mouth. The difficult mouth opening was of particular challenge to the anaesthetist. And because this was anticipated well ahead of time, the ENT team was available to establish the tracheostomy. This collaborative effort between the anaesthetist and the ENT surgeon is essential and it is advocated in clinical situations where there is an anticipated airway difficulty.

The surgical operation itself involved the maxillofacial surgeon and the ophthalmologist who handled the ankylosis release and the right eye ectropium with medial canthal repair respectively. Again, this collaborative effort resulted not only intra-operative cross fertilization of ideas, but also a reduction of overall surgical cost to the patient, chief of which is the utilization of one anaesthesia for both surgeries, more so that anaesthesia posed an enormous challenge on account of airway difficulty.

CONCLUSION

Having highlighted this multi-disciplinary approach to the management of this case, it can be observed that cooperation between various disciplines in the management of cases can be of immense benefit. This is more so in resource poor setting like ours. We therefore recommend this type of collaboration whenever and wherever it is possible.

Conflict of interest

None

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